

GEORGE ORWELL "ANIMAL FARM"

Siddiqova Madina Zohid qizi

Renessans Ta'lim Universiteti

02-21 gurux talabasi

Abstract. The article examines George Orwell's dystopian novel *Animal Farm* as one of the most significant literary works of the 20th century, representing a political allegory of totalitarian regimes. The symbolism of the characters, key themes, and plot elements such as power, propaganda, manipulation, and the betrayal of ideals are analyzed. Special attention is given to issues of social inequality and political control, revealed through the allegorical depiction of revolution and its consequences. The article also discusses the historical contexts of the work's creation and its relevance in the modern world.

Keywords: George Orwell, «Animal Farm», dystopia, political allegory, totalitarianism, propaganda, power, social inequality, manipulation, revolution.

George Orwell's novel «Animal Farm» is one of the most iconic works of world literature, which, despite its brevity, contains a powerful political and social message. Written in 1945, the novel serves as an allegory for the events surrounding the Russian Revolution of 1917 and the subsequent establishment of the totalitarian regime in the USSR. Orwell uses the image of a farm where animals rise up against their oppressor — the farmer — to depict the dynamics of revolution and its eventual degeneration into a new form of authoritarianism. Through this work, the author vividly demonstrates how the original ideals of freedom and equality can be distorted and turned into a new mechanism of oppression and exploitation.

At the heart of the novel lies the theme of power and its transformation. Orwell emphasizes that any revolution, no matter how just, can devolve into tyranny if leaders begin to use power for their personal gain. Critics often note that **Animal Farm** is one of the most powerful dystopias, exposing the mechanisms of manipulation and propaganda used to maintain authority.

The plot of the novel is built around the images of animals, each of which symbolizes a specific political or social group. For instance, the pigs, led by Napoleon, represent the communist elite who, after the revolution, appropriate all privileges for themselves, gradually becoming the new oppressors. This metaphorical portrayal of historical reality resonated with readers and critics worldwide, and many scholars view the novel as a reflection of the corruption of revolutionary ideals.

Particular attention is drawn to the theme of propaganda, which Orwell demonstrates through the character of Squealer, a pig responsible for spreading lies and distorting facts to maintain Napoleon's power. This aspect of the novel parallels real propaganda practices employed in totalitarian regimes of the 20th century, especially in the USSR and Nazi Germany.

«Animal Farm» remains relevant today, as the issues of power, manipulation of public opinion, and oppression continue to play a significant role in the political life of various countries. Many contemporary critics and scholars consider the novel a universal warning that the fight for freedom can turn into a new form of enslavement if power structures are not kept in check.

1. Historical and Cultural Context of the Novel

George Orwell's novel «Animal Farm» was written in 1943-1944, during World War II, when relations between the United Kingdom and the Soviet Union were on the rise due to their alliance against Nazi Germany. However, Orwell, being a committed socialist and a proponent of democratic values, was deeply concerned about the way totalitarian elements in the USSR were going uncriticized in the West because of wartime necessity. Orwell viewed the Soviet Union not as a

realization of socialist ideals, but rather as their distortion. «Animal Farm» became a satire on Stalinism and the political processes in the USSR, particularly on the betrayal of the ideals of the Russian Revolution of 1917 and the establishment of Joseph Stalin's dictatorship.

One of the key aspects of the historical context is the parallel between the characters in the novel and real historical figures. The leader of the pigs, Napoleon, symbolizes Stalin, while another pig, Snowball, serves as an allegory for Leon Trotsky, whose political career was destroyed due to Stalin's purges. This makes *Animal Farm* a political work in which every detail allegorically reflects the totalitarian mechanisms of power based on violence, manipulation, and propaganda.

2. Allegorical Structure and Symbolism of Characters

Orwell employs the genre of allegory to create a simple yet powerful plot in which the farm of animals represents a state, and the animals' uprising is a metaphor for revolution. The symbolism of the characters is central to the allegorical structure of the novel. Each animal represents a specific political group or social class. For instance, the working horses Boxer and Clover symbolize the working class, who remain loyal to the ideals of the revolution despite the betrayal of the elite. The pigs, led by Napoleon, become a metaphor for the party elite, who seize power under the banners of equality and justice but gradually establish a new regime of oppression.

The allegory is further emphasized by the persistent use of propaganda as a control mechanism. The character Squealer represents the propaganda machine, which distorts reality and manipulates information to strengthen Napoleon's power. As noted by researcher G. Crouch, "Orwell brilliantly demonstrates how linguistic manipulations and the alteration of historical memory can subjugate the masses' consciousness."

This system of allegories and symbols allows Orwell to depict social processes within a simplified and accessible narrative, making the novel an

effective tool of political critique. However, the allegorical form of the novel lends it a universal quality: while the action of the novel refers to specific historical events, it also addresses broader issues of power, its nature, and its inevitable abuse under totalitarianism.

3. Power and Its Transformation in the Novel

One of the central themes of «Animal Farm» is the question of the nature of power and its transformation. At the beginning of the novel, the animals' rebellion on the farm is directed against the tyranny of man — Farmer Jones, who oppresses the animals by forcing them to work in harsh conditions. However, after Jones is overthrown, the new leaders — the pigs — gradually reproduce the same forms of oppression as the previous regime. This process demonstrates the idea that power inevitably leads to corruption if it is not controlled by democratic institutions and accountability mechanisms.

Orwell shows how the revolutionary ideals of freedom and equality gradually degenerate into new forms of despotism. The slogan "All animals are equal" eventually transforms into the cynical formula: "All animals are equal, but some animals are more equal than others." This moment in the novel highlights how easily original ideals can be replaced by using language and propaganda as tools for manipulating the masses.

Orwell draws parallels between the rebellion on the farm and the events of the October Revolution of 1917 in Russia, where the initial revolutionary slogans of equality and justice were betrayed by the new ruling elite. Orwell warns that, despite good intentions, any revolution can lead to dictatorship if power becomes concentrated in the hands of a small group. The theme of power in the novel unfolds as a continuous process of its concentration and use to strengthen the position of the new elite.

4. Propaganda and Manipulation of Consciousness

One of the key tools of power in the novel is propaganda, through which the pigs justify their behavior and control the other animals. Propaganda in «Animal

Farm» is embodied by the character Squealer, who skillfully distorts reality to maintain Napoleon's authority. For example, when the pigs openly begin to break the rules established after the revolution, Squealer explains that the pigs "need" special privileges to better manage the farm.

Propaganda plays a central role in maintaining the dictatorship, showing how language can be used to control thoughts and behavior. Manipulation of facts, the creation of false narratives, and the gradual rewriting of reality through the recoding of language are all used as tools of subjugation and control of the masses. Orwell demonstrates how by distorting the truth and manipulating consciousness, a society can be kept in a state of constant submission, reflecting the real mechanisms employed in totalitarian regimes of the 20th century.

5. The Universality of the Theme and Its Relevance

«Animal Farm» was written in a specific historical context, but its themes remain relevant today. Issues of manipulation, abuse of power, and oppression continue to play a significant role in modern societies. Political regimes that use the language of propaganda to justify their authority still exist, and the mechanisms of control through distortion of information, as depicted in the novel, have become even more sophisticated.

Orwell, in his work, warns that the threat of totalitarianism and the suppression of democratic ideals exists in any society where mechanisms of power control are absent. This aspect of the novel makes it a universal warning, relevant not only for the 20th century but also for the modern world.

George Orwell's novel «Animal Farm» is not just an allegory of the Russian Revolution and Stalinism, but a profound critique of all forms of totalitarianism and oppression. Orwell uses a simple and accessible narrative to expose the complex political processes occurring in society, emphasizing how easily power can be distorted and used for suppression. Issues of manipulation of consciousness, abuse of power, and the betrayal of revolutionary ideals make the novel relevant

not only in its historical context but also in modern society, highlighting its universality and importance.

George Orwell's novel «Animal Farm» is one of the most significant political works of the 20th century, serving as a powerful allegory of totalitarian regimes and revealing the mechanisms of power, manipulation, and oppression. Through the seemingly simple story of an animal uprising on a farm, Orwell addresses fundamental questions about the nature of power, its transformation, and the inevitable corruption that accompanies any revolutionary process.

The allegorical structure of the novel allows «Animal Farm» to be viewed as a universal work, transcending its specific historical context. Themes of betrayal of ideals, the use of propaganda to manipulate the masses, and the concentration of power in the hands of a narrow elite remain relevant in today's political landscape. Orwell illustrates how the fight for freedom can turn into new forms of oppression if power is not constrained by democratic checks and balances.

«Animal Farm» serves as a warning about how easily the ideals of justice and equality can be distorted and turned into tools of suppression. The novel's relevance is confirmed by ongoing political processes worldwide, where issues of power, manipulation of public opinion, and human rights violations remain at the forefront. Orwell's work is a reminder of the importance of not only revolutionary change but also the establishment of sustainable democratic institutions capable of protecting society from repeating the mistakes of the past.

References:

1. Crouch, G. Propaganda and Power in 20th Century Literature. — Moscow: Logos, 2009.
2. Ivanov, A. N. Allegorical Images in the Works of George Orwell. — Moscow: Nauka, 2010.
3. Smith, D. J. George Orwell and His World: From Dystopia to Allegory. — St. Petersburg: Piter, 2005.

4. Brown, P. History of Totalitarian Regimes in the 20th Century. — London: Routledge, 2003.

5. Brodsky, I. A. Orwell: Politics and Literature. — Moscow: Logos, 1998.